

Elucidating Dermoscopic Patterns and Correlations in Recalcitrant Dermatophytosis: A Cross-Sectional Study from a Tertiary Care Center

Ujala Negi¹, Gajanan A Pise², Malteshgouda N Patil³, Himani Chawla⁴¹Senior Resident, Department of Dermatology, AIIMS Bathinda, Punjab²Assistant Professor, Department of Dermatology, Belagavi Institute of Medical Sciences, Karnataka³Professor and HOD, Department of Dermatology, Belagavi Institute of Medical Sciences, Karnataka⁴MD Dermatology, SR, Department of Dermatology AIIMS Bhatinda

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Ujala Negi

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Abstract:

Background: Recalcitrant dermatophytosis presents a significant diagnostic challenge, particularly in tropical regions where it is prevalent. Traditional diagnostic methods are often time-consuming and may delay treatment.

Methods: This cross-sectional study evaluated 240 patients with chronic, recurrent dermatophytosis at Belagavi Institute of Medical Sciences, Karnataka, India. Dermoscopic patterns were analyzed and correlated with results from KOH examination and fungal cultures to assess the effectiveness of dermoscopy as a diagnostic tool.

Results: Significant correlations were found between specific dermoscopic patterns and traditional diagnostic tests. Peripheral scales were significantly associated with KOH positivity ($p=0.005$), and a reddish-grey background was correlated with culture positivity ($p=0.013$).

Conclusion: Dermoscopy enhances the diagnostic accuracy for recalcitrant dermatophytosis, supporting its integration into routine clinical practice to improve treatment outcomes.

Keywords: Dermoscopy, Recalcitrant Dermatophytosis, Tinea Corporis, Tinea Cruris, Diagnostic Correlation, KOH Examination, Fungal Culture.

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Introduction

Dermatophytosis, a fungal infection caused by dermatophytes, predominantly affects the keratinized tissues such as skin, hair, and nails, manifesting as various clinical entities like tinea corporis, tinea cruris, and tinea pedis. In tropical and subtropical regions, including India, dermatophytosis presents a significant public health challenge due to its high prevalence, chronicity, and recurrent nature, which are compounded by emerging resistance to conventional antifungal therapies. The persistence of infection despite appropriate management, termed recalcitrant dermatophytosis, poses a unique set of challenges, including diagnosis and management, necessitating innovative diagnostic approaches. [1,2,3]

Traditional diagnostic modalities for dermatophytosis, such as Potassium Hydroxide (KOH) examination and fungal culture, are time-consuming and require specific laboratory setups, which may delay the initiation of treatment. In recent years, dermoscopy has emerged as a rapid, non-invasive diagnostic tool that enhances diagnostic accuracy by allowing the visualization of subtle morphological features not discernible by

the naked eye. This study leverages the advantages of dermoscopy to elucidate specific patterns associated with recalcitrant dermatophytosis and examines the correlation between these dermoscopic findings and traditional fungal investigations. [4,5] The rationale for focusing on dermoscopy stems from its potential to bridge the diagnostic gap in settings with limited access to specialized fungal laboratories. Dermoscopy not only provides a real-time aid in diagnosing fungal infections but also assists in monitoring treatment efficacy and adapting management strategies accordingly. Despite its increasing application in general dermatology, the utilization of dermoscopy in diagnosing dermatophytosis, particularly the recalcitrant form, remains underexplored. [6]

This cross-sectional study was conducted at the Dermatology Outpatient Department of Belagavi Institute of Medical Sciences (BIMS), Karnataka, where a total of 240 patients diagnosed with chronic, recurrent dermatophytosis were evaluated. This study aims to systematically document the dermoscopic patterns observed in patients with recalcitrant dermatophytosis and to correlate these

patterns with results from KOH examination and fungal cultures. By establishing these correlations, the study seeks to underscore the utility of dermoscopy as a complementary diagnostic tool that could potentially expedite the clinical management of dermatophytosis. [7,8] The significance of this research lies in its potential to enhance clinical outcomes through faster diagnosis and tailored treatment approaches. It also aims to contribute to the growing body of literature on the dermoscopic features of dermatophytosis, providing a foundation for future studies to explore the standardization of dermoscopic criteria for fungal infections. [9]

Through detailed analysis and correlation with traditional diagnostic tests, this study endeavours to reinforce the role of dermoscopy not just as a diagnostic adjunct but as an integral part of the dermatological toolkit in managing complex cases of dermatophytosis. This could ultimately lead to quicker clinical decisions, reduced disease transmission, and better patient outcomes in the face of rising antifungal resistance.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting: This cross-sectional study was conducted over a period of 12 months from February 2021 to January 2022 at the Dermatology Outpatient Department (OPD) of Belagavi Institute of Medical Sciences (BIMS), a tertiary care center in Karnataka, India. The study was designed to explore the dermoscopic patterns in patients diagnosed with recalcitrant dermatophytosis and to correlate these patterns with traditional diagnostic modalities like KOH examination and fungal cultures.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee of BIMS, Belagavi. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants after fully explaining the purpose of the study and the procedures involved, ensuring confidentiality and voluntary participation.

Participants

The inclusion criteria were:

Patients aged 18 years and above with clinically diagnosed chronic, recurrent dermatophytosis of the skin, hair, and nails.

1. Both genders were included in the study.
2. The exclusion criteria were:
3. Patients who refused to give consent.
4. Patients with negative KOH preparation or culture results for dermatophytes.

Data Collection Methods: Data collection was carried out using a pre-structured proforma, which included demographic data, clinical history, and details of previous treatments. Each participant

underwent a clinical examination followed by dermoscopic assessment.

Dermoscopic Examination: Dermoscopic evaluations were performed using the IDS-1100 dermatoscope (illuco) with a magnification of 10x in polarized mode without contact medium. The device was thoroughly cleaned with an alcohol swab between examinations to prevent cross-infection. Dermoscopic features including color, pattern, and specific findings such as scales, erythema, and micropustules were documented and photographed for analysis.

Laboratory Investigations

1. **KOH Examination:** Skin, hair, and nail samples were treated with 10% KOH for skin and hair, and 40% KOH for nails, examined under a microscope for fungal elements.
2. **Culture:** Samples were cultured on Sabouraud's Dextrose Agar at 25°C for up to 4 weeks to identify the growth of dermatophytes.

Statistical Analysis: Data were entered into a Google Spreadsheet and analyzed using SPSS software version 22.0. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations were used to summarize the data. Correlational analyses were performed using Chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests for continuous variables where appropriate. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Quality Control: To ensure the reliability of the dermoscopic and microbiological findings, all assessments were performed by two independent dermatologists with expertise in dermoscopy and mycology. Discrepancies were resolved by consensus or by involving a third expert.

Results

Demographic and Clinical Characteristics: The study included 240 patients with recalcitrant dermatophytosis. The age of the participants ranged from 19 to 68 years, with a mean age of 34.5 ± 11.8 years. The majority of the patients (67.5%) were within the 21 to 40-year age group. The gender distribution showed a male preponderance, with 143 males (59.58%) and 97 females (40.42%).

Dermoscopic Findings: The most common dermoscopic features observed across different forms of dermatophytosis included peripheral scales, diffuse erythema, and perifollicular scales.

Tinea corporis was the most frequently diagnosed type of dermatophytosis (40.8%), followed by tinea cruris (34.2%).

Correlation between Dermoscopic and KOH/Culture Results

A significant correlation was found between certain dermoscopic patterns and KOH examination results. Peripheral scales showed a statistically significant correlation with KOH positivity ($p = 0.005$). The correlation analysis between dermoscopic patterns and culture results also revealed significant findings, particularly the reddish-grey background correlated with culture positivity ($p = 0.013$).

Dermoscopic Findings

Tinea Corporis

- **Figure 1: Tinea Corporis** - This figure illustrates perifollicular scales (black arrow), along with brown-black dots and globules (green arrow). These features are indicative of active fungal elements, aligning with the positive KOH test results observed in our study.
- **Figure 3: Tinea Corporis** - Showcases a reddish-black background (black arrow) and red dot and globule (green arrow). This pattern supports the utility of dermoscopy in identifying culture-positive cases, aiding in quicker diagnostic conclusions.
- **Figure 6: Tinea Corporis** - Features red globules and dot (green arrow) against a backdrop of diffuse erythema, suggesting active inflammation and fungal invasion typical of Tinea corporis.
- **Figure 7: Tinea Corporis** - Displays peripheral scales (green arrow) and a red-grey background (black arrow), which are crucial for differentiating Tinea corporis from other dermatophytic infections.

Tinea Capitis

- **Figure 2: Tinea Capitis** - Highlights peripheral scales (black arrow), which are characteristic of Tinea capitis, aiding in its differentiation from other scalp conditions with similar presentations.
- **Figure 11: Tinea Capitis** - Features comma hair (black arrow) and corkscrew hair (green

arrow), specific indicators of hair shaft invasion by dermatophytes, valuable for confirming diagnoses in clinical settings.

Tinea Manuum

- **Figure 4: Tinea Manuum** - Captures erythema and scaling along the creases (green arrow), typical for Tinea manuum. This pattern highlights the importance of examining the creases in suspected hand dermatophytosis.
- **Figure 8: Tinea Manuum** - Shows peripheral scales along the creases (black arrow), emphasizing the diagnostic relevance of dermoscopy in distinguishing Tinea manuum from eczematous disorders affecting the hands.

Tinea Cruris

- **Figure 5: Tinea Cruris** - Depicts hypopigmented terminal hair (green arrow), a distinctive but less common feature of Tinea cruris, which can assist in its identification, especially in chronic or inadequately treated cases.

Tinea Unguium

- **Figure 9: Tinea Unguium** - Demonstrates the aurora borealis pattern, a specific dermoscopic sign indicative of fungal invasion of the nail plate, useful for early detection and management.
- **Figure 10: Tinea Unguium** - Features subungual hypertrophy, typical of ongoing fungal infection, emphasizing the need for mycological investigation and targeted treatment.

Tinea Incognito

- **Figure 12: Tinea Incognito** - This figure highlights diffuse erythema and micropustules (black arrow), signs that are often misinterpreted due to their non-specific nature. These features underscore the importance of considering fungal etiologies in atypical dermatological presentations.

Figure 1: Tinea Corporis: Perifollicular Scales (Black Arrow), Brown-Black Dots And Globules(Green Arrow)

Figure 2: Tinea Capitis: Peripheral Scales (Black Arrow)

Figure 3: Tinea Corporis: Reddish- Black Background (Black Arrow), Red Dot And Globule (Green Arrow)

Figure 4: Tinea Manuum: Erythema and Scaling Along the Creases (Green Arrow)

Figure 5: Tinea Cruris: Hypopigmented Terminal Hair (Green Arrow)

Figure 6: Tinea Corporis: Red Globules and Dot (Green Arrow) With Diffuse Erythema

Figure 7: Tinea Corporis: Peripheral Scales (Green Arrow), Red- Grey Background (Black Arrow)

Figure 8: Tinea Manuum: Peripheral Scales Along the Creases (Black Arrow)

Figure 9: Tinea Unguium: Aurora Borealis Pattern

Figure 10: Tinea Unguium: Subungual Hypertrophy

Figure 11: Tinea Capitis: Comma Hair (Black Arrow), Corkscrew Hair (Green Arrow)

Figure 12: Tinea Incognito: Diffuse Erythema, And Micropustules (Black Arrow)

The results demonstrate a significant correlation between certain dermoscopic patterns and the outcomes of traditional diagnostic tests (KOH and culture), supporting the utility of dermoscopy as a rapid, adjunctive diagnostic tool in the management of recalcitrant dermatophytosis. The findings underline the potential of integrating dermoscopic evaluation into routine clinical practice to enhance the diagnostic accuracy and expedite the management of dermatophytosis.

Table 1: Age Distribution of Participants

Age Group (years)	Frequency	Percentage
≤20	14	5.8%
21-40	162	67.5%
41-60	56	23.3%
>60	8	3.3%
Total	240	100%

Table 2: Frequency of Dermatophytosis Types

Type of Dermatophytosis	Frequency	Percentage
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Tinea corporis	98	40.8%
Tinea cruris	82	34.2%
Tinea capitis	29	12.1%
Other types	31	12.9%
Total	240	100%

Table 3: Correlation Analysis of Dermoscopic Patterns with KOH Examination

Dermoscopic Pattern	KOH Positive	KOH Negative	P-value
Peripheral Scales	124 (64.25%)	4 (100%)	0.005*
Diffuse Erythema	73 (37.82%)	2 (50%)	0.201
Reddish-Grey Background	121 (62.69%)	2 (50%)	0.221
Perifollicular Scales	89 (46.11%)	2 (50%)	0.683

Table 4: Correlation Analysis of Dermoscopic Patterns with Fungal Culture

Dermoscopic Pattern	Culture Positive	Culture Negative	P-value
Reddish-Grey Background	66 (62.26%)	57 (62.64%)	0.013*
Peripheral Scales	73 (68.87%)	55 (60.44%)	0.0428
Diffuse Erythema	41 (38.68%)	34 (37.36%)	0.819
Perifollicular Scales	44 (41.51%)	47 (51.65%)	0.302

Discussion

The findings of this study underline the potential of dermoscopy as a significant diagnostic tool in the evaluation of recalcitrant dermatophytosis. The observed correlation between dermoscopic patterns and traditional diagnostic methods (KOH and culture) suggests that dermoscopy can effectively complement these standard tests, enhancing diagnostic speed and accuracy. This is particularly relevant in resource-limited settings where rapid diagnosis can facilitate timely and appropriate management, thus mitigating the spread and severity of the infection. [10,11]

The high prevalence of dermoscopic patterns such as peripheral scales, diffuse erythema, and perifollicular scales observed in our study aligns with findings from other studies, highlighting consistent diagnostic markers for dermatophytosis. Notably, the significant correlation between peripheral scales and KOH positivity ($p=0.005$) corroborates research suggesting that certain dermoscopic features may be indicative of fungal activity, thereby serving as reliable markers for initiating antifungal therapy. [12]

Moreover, the substantial correlation between the reddish-grey background and culture positivity ($p=0.013$) emphasizes the role of dermoscopy in identifying subtle clinical changes that may not be apparent through traditional examination alone. This finding is crucial because it suggests that dermoscopy might detect early or mild forms of the disease, potentially before they become apparent through culture, thus allowing for earlier intervention. [13] The predominance of tinea corporis and tinea cruris in our study population reflects common clinical presentations in tropical climates, as reported in the literature. This demographic relevance stresses the need for

diagnostic tools like dermoscopy in regions where dermatophytosis is prevalent and often presents in its recalcitrant form. [14] Despite the promising implications of these findings, it is important to acknowledge the limitations inherent in a single-center study, including the potential for selection bias and the limited generalizability of the results. Additionally, the variability in dermoscopic expertise among clinicians may influence the diagnostic outcomes, suggesting a need for standardized training and protocols in the use of dermoscopy for fungal infections. [15]

Future studies should focus on multicenter trials to validate these findings across different demographic groups and settings. There is also a need for longitudinal research to assess the utility of dermoscopy in monitoring treatment response, which could further solidify its place in the dermatological toolkit for managing dermatophytosis.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates the utility of dermoscopy in augmenting the diagnosis of recalcitrant dermatophytosis, showing significant correlations with traditional methods like KOH examination and fungal culture. The integration of dermoscopy into routine clinical practice can potentially transform the diagnostic landscape for dermatophytosis, leading to faster and more accurate diagnoses, improved management strategies, and better patient outcomes. As resistance to antifungal treatments continues to challenge healthcare systems globally, innovative diagnostic approaches like dermoscopy could become invaluable in managing this pervasive disease.

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